

SYSTEM OF ORGANIZATION AND COORDINATION OF LEGAL AWARENESS ACTIVITIES OF INTERNAL AFFAIRS BODIES

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Abstract. The article reflects the concept of legal advocacy, which is one of the important areas of legal support activities of internal affairs bodies, its legal basis and essence, organizational and legal forms of implementing legal advocacy, and the rights and obligations of the sectoral branches of internal affairs bodies in raising legal awareness and legal culture in society.

Keywords. Advocacy, legal advocacy, legal awareness, legal culture, legal support activities, civil society, democratic rule of law, legal literacy, legal information

In recent years, large-scale reforms have been carried out in the sphere of fundamental reform of the national legal system, the formation of a legal culture in society, the training of qualified legal personnel, and legal advocacy.

In order to coordinate work in this direction, on January 9, 2019, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. UP-5618 "On the Fundamental Improvement of the System for Raising Legal Awareness and Legal Culture in Society" was adopted[1].

The Decree provides for further increasing the effectiveness of work to raise the legal awareness and legal culture of the population, introducing modern methods of increasing the legal knowledge of citizens in accordance with socio-political changes, as well as forming a strong legal immunity to protect the population, especially young people, from harmful information.

As a result of ensuring the implementation of this Decree:

- a) a system for monitoring and assessing legal culture in society has been introduced;
- b) minimum requirements for the level of legal literacy of the population have been developed;
- c) new approaches have emerged to increasing the legal culture and social activity of the population in the interaction of the citizen, the state, and society, ensuring a balance between personal and social needs;

new projects have been developed for the consistent introduction of initial legal concepts and rules of conduct into the consciousness of children and youth, and for the integrated and systematic conduct of legal education and upbringing.

Propaganda (Arabic, interest, dissemination) - in a broad sense, a special type of social activity, the promotion of scientific, artistic, socio-political, national ideas and values in order to increase the socio-political activity of the population. In the process of propaganda, the achievements of science, art, politics, and ideology are widely popularized, enriched, and further developed. In a narrow sense, activity aimed at promoting ideology and politics. Propaganda should be based on the principles of scientificity, concreteness, objectivity, and close connection with social life, and should be organized. Propaganda (from Lat. propaganda

- information to be disseminated) - activity aimed at popularizing certain ideas in public consciousness through oral or mass media[2].

Legal advocacy is a process that represents a systematic and purposeful activity aimed at instilling legal order and principles in the peoples of a certain group, nation, society, race, ethnic group, territory. It can be recognized as a concept that means a set of methods and practical actions aimed at calling citizens to vigilance against spiritual aggression, understanding the essence of existing dangers and threats, forming public opinion about them, and most importantly, uniting and consolidating the people on the basis of the national idea, educating in the minds and hearts of the younger generation a sense of loyalty to noble ideas.

When carrying out legal advocacy, the main attention is paid to the issue of legal awareness and culture.

Legal consciousness is understood as people's understanding and knowledge of law, as well as the reflection of ideas about law in human consciousness. Legal consciousness is one of the forms of social consciousness. Consequently, it is not the only form of consciousness. The spheres of life are extremely diverse, each of which manifests itself in the social consciousness of society in specific forms: religious, political, legal, moral, and others. Regardless of the specifics and individuality of the field being studied, each form of social consciousness develops in close connection with other forms. Sometimes, the state of mutual harmony between different forms of social consciousness creates certain difficulties, and it is not easy to separate them[3].

Legal culture is understood as the legislative level of society, the level of public awareness of existing laws, the observance of legal norms by citizens and officials, and intolerance towards those who do not comply with them. Legal culture is conditionally divided into the legal culture of society and the individual. The legal culture of society is considered as a type of social culture, reflecting a certain level of legal consciousness, legality, the improvement of laws and legal experience, and encompassing all the wealth created by humanity in the field of law. The legal culture of society is the basis for ensuring the freedom and security of the individual, human rights, their legal protection, and social activity. The legal culture of the individual is an integral part of the legal culture of society. This activity corresponds to the development of society and its culture in the field of law, as a result of which a constant legal enrichment of the individual and society occurs. Undoubtedly, a person's high legal culture ensures the development of society. In almost all his speeches, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan emphasizes the importance of legal culture and issues of its enhancement. For example, in his report dedicated to the 24th anniversary of the adoption of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan (December 7, 2016), he stated: "In ensuring the rule of law, it is important to raise legal culture and educate citizens in the spirit of respect for the law"[4].

The main tasks of enhancing legal awareness and legal culture in society are:

Establishing a system to consistently convey to the population the essence and content of ongoing socio-economic reforms, adopted legislative acts, and state programs in the country, reinforcing in citizens' minds the vital idea that "Instilling a spirit of respect for the law in society is the key to building a democratic state governed by the rule of law!";

In raising legal awareness and legal culture in society, paying special attention, first and foremost, to the systematic and integrated implementation of education and upbringing,

instilling legal awareness and legal culture in all segments of the population, starting from the preschool education system, promoting ideas of maintaining a balance between personal and societal interests;

Deeply instilling in the younger generation's consciousness the concepts of rights and duties, honesty and integrity, as well as moral and ethical norms, teaching them the most important aspects of the Constitution from childhood;

Organizing legal and educational activities to form legal culture among the population in conjunction with the study of our people's history, religion, and national values, as well as strengthening a sense of belonging to the country and patriotism by fostering pride in state symbols in every citizen;

Continuously raising the legal awareness and legal culture of civil servants, cultivating in them an intolerant attitude towards corruption and other offenses;

Strengthening the collaboration between state authorities and administration bodies, including law enforcement agencies and civil society institutions, in carrying out targeted legal advocacy;

Systematically establishing the widespread and effective use of social partnership principles in organizing activities to enhance legal awareness and legal culture in society;

Increasing the role of mass media in providing legal information, expanding the use of innovative methods of legal advocacy, including the application of web technologies;

Improving legal education, as well as developing the system of training, retraining, and advanced training of legal personnel;

Conducting in-depth studies of the scientific foundations for enhancing legal awareness and legal culture in society.

The introduction of innovative methods of legal advocacy in raising legal culture in society is an important process, and a number of important works are currently being carried out in this area:

Establishment of the National Legal Internet Portal of the Republic of Uzbekistan;

Implementation of the Advice.uz legal information system, which offers legal solutions for various life situations and connects with the electronic system for providing public services;

launch of the "Legal Test" system with various stages on the website <https://huquqiportal.uz/> in order to test the level of legal knowledge of citizens;

creation of channels of state bodies and organizations on social networks on the Internet (Facebook, Telegram, Twitter, Youtube, Mytube.uz, etc.) and placement of legal advocacy materials on these channels, based on the areas of activity of the sphere, with the widespread use of web technologies;

Creation on the Internet of the National Database of Legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan - Lex.uz website and the telegram channel "Huquqiy axborot" in Uzbek, Russian and English languages, providing brief analytical coverage of the content of legislative acts, as well as legal materials to improve the legal knowledge of the population, etc.

In order to ensure the implementation of the resolutions of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 16, 2022 No. 259 "On Approval of the Program of Measures to Enhance Legal Culture in Society for 2022-2023" and dated February 17, 2022 No. 74 "On Measures for Further Improvement of the System of Monitoring and Evaluation of Measures to Enhance Legal Culture in Society," as well as in order to further improve

measures to increase the effectiveness of legal awareness-raising work, the implementation of legal awareness-raising work in internal affairs bodies is of great practical importance[5].

The main tasks in raising the legal awareness and culture of employees and the public in the internal affairs bodies are:

Formation of a system for consistently conveying the essence and content of ongoing reforms and adopted regulatory legal acts, instilling the vital idea that "establishing a spirit of respect for laws in society is the key to building a democratic state governed by the rule of law!";

strengthening a sense of involvement and patriotism in the reforms being carried out in the sphere of internal affairs bodies, wide promotion of the idea of "Serving the interests of the people" among employees of higher, middle, and lower levels of subdivisions;

Strengthening the responsibility of managers for the widespread use of innovative methods in the implementation of promotional activities, expanding the use of web technologies in providing legal information;

regular communication of the essence and significance of the reforms being carried out in the internal affairs bodies, adopted legislative acts and state programs;

organization of legal and educational activities in conjunction with the study of the history, religion, and national values of our people;

formation of an intolerant attitude towards corruption and other offenses;

strengthening the interaction of other law enforcement agencies and civil society institutions in carrying out targeted legal advocacy;

increasing the role of the mass media in providing legal information, wide use of innovative methods of legal advocacy;

In-depth study of the fundamentals of raising legal awareness and legal culture in internal affairs bodies.

Work aimed at improving the legal culture of internal affairs bodies is carried out by responsible sectoral service employees through systematic promotion of the norms of legislative acts, conveying the essence and significance of the reforms being carried out in the system of internal affairs bodies.

Work aimed at improving legal culture can also be carried out by preparing and broadcasting necessary information-analytical and visual media materials on legislative innovations in the form of video clips.

Coordination of legal advocacy activities in the system of the Ministry of Internal Affairs is carried out by the Legal Advocacy and Human Rights Protection Department of the Legal Support Department of the Organizational Department.

The Department of Legal Promotion and Protection of Human Rights of the Legal Support Department is assigned the following tasks:

ensuring the implementation of state legal policy in internal affairs bodies, studying law enforcement practice and activities on legal advocacy;

Coordination of the activities of internal affairs bodies in carrying out legal advocacy;

organization of cooperation with law enforcement agencies, as well as bodies of citizen self-government, non-governmental non-profit organizations and international organizations on issues of legal advocacy;

participation in work to raise legal awareness and legal culture in society, as well as organizing the promotion of the essence and significance of legislative acts among employees of internal affairs bodies in order to strengthen legality;

taking measures to provide the fund of normative legal acts with codes, laws and their commentaries, newsletters and other legal literature, submitting proposals to the Ministry's management on subscriptions to legal publications;

analysis of the state of observance of human rights and freedoms and coordination of the activities of subordinate structures;

study, analysis of existing problems in the law enforcement practice of internal affairs bodies and development of proposals on measures to eliminate them;

ensuring the implementation of state legal policy in internal affairs bodies;

development of methodological manuals on the preparation of draft normative legal acts in internal affairs bodies;

studying the state of work on the preparation and adoption of draft normative legal acts in internal affairs bodies, participating in the development, implementation, and control over the implementation of current and long-term plans for rule-making activities.

The Investigative Department, the Department of Spiritual and Educational Work and Personnel Support, the Department of Public Security, the Department of Public Relations and Mass Media, and the Department of Legal Support are equally responsible for conducting awareness-raising events in cooperation with other state bodies and organizations, including courts, law enforcement agencies, and educational institutions, and for entering information from such events into the electronic portal.

Employees of the relevant sectoral and territorial subdivisions of the internal affairs bodies, employees of the legal service, and in their absence, employees of personnel units are responsible for conducting awareness-raising events in the territorial subdivisions of the internal affairs bodies.

The Legal Support Department coordinates the entry of information on the work carried out by the structural subdivisions of the Ministry on promotional activities into the electronic portal, summarizes and monitors reports on the work done in this area.

By studying the needs of employees of internal affairs bodies and the population for legal information, including by analyzing appeals received on the official pages of the Ministry on the Internet, the most common legal problems will be identified, and promotional materials (brochures, infographics, videos, slides, annotations, comics) will be prepared and organized in this direction.

At the same time, issues of concern to the population are analyzed, and video clips with legal explanations are prepared and distributed with the participation of specialists in the relevant field.

In order to enhance the intellectual potential, worldview, and professional skills of internal affairs officers, and to familiarize them with legislative innovations and global events, the content of regulatory legal and internal departmental documents adopted to improve the activities of internal affairs bodies will be regularly brought to the attention of personnel during "Spirituality and Enlightenment Lessons" on Saturdays.

Legislative acts, internal departmental acts, which must be brought to the attention of employees of internal affairs bodies, are regularly published in the newspapers "Postda - Na postu" or the magazine "Qalqon - Shit."

Video clips providing for the weekly dissemination to employees of the internal affairs bodies and the public of adopted legislative acts, political and legal reforms being carried out in the country, will be filmed and posted on the World Wide Web.

In order to study the state of raising legal culture in society and the effectiveness of practical work in this area, surveys are conducted to determine the legal knowledge of the population on specific life issues.

Heads of sectoral services and territorial subdivisions, designated as responsible for promotional activities, are personally responsible for the timely, complete, and high-quality implementation of the relevant measures and the entry of relevant information on the work performed into the electronic portal within three days from the date of their implementation. In conclusion, it should be noted that familiarizing the population and members of society with the legal foundations of reforms, providing them with legal information and literature, conveying objective information about the traditions of national statehood to young people, and further improving public opinion by informing citizens about the latest changes in the life of the state and society demonstrate the necessity of organizing legal advocacy work in internal affairs bodies.

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